

**E5.5 Final prototype for data aggregation
for self-optimization processes on network
operations**

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Contribuyentes	Juan Sebastian Camargo
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List of Acronyms

3D	Three Dimension
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIOps	AI Operations
AR	Augmented Reality
CD	Continuous Delivery
CI	Continuous Integration
6DoF	Six Degrees of Freedom
FPS	Frame per Second
HD	High Definition
HTC	Holographic-Type Communications
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
ML	Machine Learning
MLOps	Machine Learning Operations
NFV	Network Function Virtualization
NR	New Radio
QoE	Quality of Experience
RAN	Radio Access Network
SoA	State-of-the-Art
TD	Technological Domain
UE	User Equipment
UNICO	Universalización de Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión
VNF	Virtual Network Function
VR	Virtual Reality
XR	Extended Reality

1 Introduction

In the rapidly evolving landscape of network operations, the ability to self-optimize has become essential for maintaining optimal performance and adapting to dynamic conditions. Data aggregation is at the heart of these self-optimization processes, serving as the foundation for intelligent decision-making. Our final prototype uses this approach by deploying an ML model using Kubeflow Pipelines, which acts as the intelligent core of the cloud-based solution.

The ML model uses data from a Feature Store for online inference, ensuring access to the most relevant and up-to-date information. This continuous stream of aggregated data allows the model to make accurate predictions and adjustments in real-time, enhancing the network's ability to self-optimize. By exporting the model's output to a Holoportation application, we demonstrate a practical application of our system, where intelligent data processing meets immersive user experiences. This integration highlights the seamless flow of data from aggregation to actionable insights, ultimately improving network performance and user satisfaction.

The final prototype highlights the critical importance of data aggregation in facilitating self-optimization within cloud environments. By using Kubeflow Pipelines interconnected with a Feature Store, we have established a scalable and efficient pipeline for data processing and ML deployment. This framework not only improves the operational efficiency of network systems but also presents the transformative potential of combining machine learning with innovative technologies like Holoportation. Through this document, we illustrate how intelligent data aggregation is indispensable for advancing modern network operations.

2 Conceptual description

In cloud environments, data aggregation serves as a critical point for self-optimization processes, allowing systems to adapt dynamically to changing conditions and workloads. Data aggregation involves collecting data from diverse sources to create a comprehensive dataset that reflects the current state and performance metrics of the network operations. This aggregated data becomes the critical point for machine learning (ML) models to analyse patterns, predict future states, and make informed decisions that optimize network performance.

At the core of self-optimization is the ability to process large volumes of data in real-time, which needs efficient data aggregation mechanisms. In a cloud environment, data sources can include system logs, performance metrics, user behaviour data, and external factors. Aggregating this data involves not only gathering it but also transforming and normalizing it to ensure consistency and relevance for analysis.

The ML models deployed, orchestrated using Kubeflow Pipelines, rely heavily on this aggregated data to perform online inference. By accessing a Feature Store, the models retrieve the most up-to-date features necessary for accurate predictions and decision-making. The Feature Store acts as a centralized repository that serves preprocessed and curated feature data to the ML models, ensuring consistency between training and inference phases. This alignment is crucial for the models to generalize well and adapt to new data patterns, thereby enhancing the self-optimization capabilities of the system.

Once the ML models generate the actions, these outputs are then exported to applications that can utilize them effectively. For instance, integrating with a Holoportation application allows for immersive visualization and interaction with the data and model outputs. This application can provide real-time feedback and control mechanisms, enabling users or automated systems to respond promptly to the insights generated.

In implementing data aggregation for self-optimization, several technical considerations are important¹:

Scalability: The data aggregation framework must scale horizontally to accommodate increasing data volumes without compromising performance. Utilizing cloud-native technologies and microservices architectures can help achieve this scalability.

Data Quality and Consistency: Ensuring that the aggregated data is accurate, consistent, and up-to-date is essential. This involves implementing data validation, cleansing processes, and synchronization mechanisms across different data sources.

¹Lorido-Botran, T., Miguel-Alonso, J., & Lozano, J. A. (2014). "Auto-Scaling Techniques for Elastic Applications in Cloud Environments."

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Low Latency: For real-time self-optimization, the latency between data generation, aggregation, and ML inference must be minimized. This may involve edge computing strategies and in-memory data processing technologies.

Security and Compliance: Aggregated data often includes sensitive information. Implementing robust security measures, such as encryption and access controls, is necessary to protect data integrity and comply with regulatory requirements.

Integration with ML Pipelines: Seamless integration between data aggregation layers and ML pipelines ensures that the models receive the right data at the right time. Tools like Kubeflow facilitate the orchestration of complex ML workflows in cloud environments.

In conclusion, data aggregation is an indispensable component of self-optimization in cloud environments, as the ones described in 6GEnablers-AI. It provides the necessary data foundation for ML models to generate meaningful actions, which in turn guide the optimization of network operations. By addressing technical challenges and using advanced tools and frameworks, organizations can build efficient and responsive systems capable of adapting to the ever-evolving demands of modern network infrastructures.

3 Configuration and usage

As can be seen in Figure 1, we can see the interaction between i2CATs ML Module and OPTARE’s Feature Store. As described previously, the interconnection between the feature store and the ML intelligent entity is vital for maintaining consistency and efficiency in machine learning workflows. The feature store serves as a centralized repository of curated, preprocessed features that are used by the ML models for both training and real-time inference. This synergy is essential for enabling self-optimization processes, as it allows the ML models to adapt quickly to new information and optimize network operations effectively in cloud environments.

Figure 1 Data flow in the cloud infrastructure.

The access to the Feature Store is done using API Calls. This offers flexibility and modularity, allowing different services to communicate seamlessly regardless of their underlying technologies. This approach enables independent development and scaling of modules, simplifies maintenance, and facilitates the integration of new features without disrupting the entire system. We can see the Swagger UI for the API calls in the Feature Store described in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Data Aggregation using API Calls in the FEAST.

The result can be observed in the following snippet, at Figure 3:

```
{'container_cpu_time': 0.4078509091,  
'container_cpu_utilization': 0.0023405235,  
'deployment': 'dummy-python-deployment',  
'event_date': '2024-08-02',  
'event_time': '14:00:00',  
'event_timestamp': 1722607200000,  
'k8s_pod_cpu_time': 0.394327,  
'k8s_pod_cpu_utilization': 0.0007106301,  
'k8s_pod_network_io': 10485.5454545455}]
```

Figure 3 Data gathering for offline inference.

After having obtained the data, we need to perform a more in-depth statistical aggregation based on the cumulative distribution function (CDF). This will help us represent a robust and versatile approach for analyzing and summarizing large datasets. This methodology enables the transformation of raw data into actionable insights by capturing the cumulative probability structure of the dataset. By using CDF, it becomes possible to examine data distributions at various levels of granularity, such as temporal intervals, spatial regions, or categorical dimensions. This granular exploration facilitates the identification of critical metrics, trends, and anomalies while enabling meaningful comparisons across different groups or categories. Furthermore, the use of CDF enhances the interpretability of aggregated data by reducing noise and variability, allowing analysts to discern underlying patterns and relationships more effectively.

The CDF-based approach is particularly advantageous for detecting and quantifying statistical properties, such as outliers, thresholds, and percentiles, that are otherwise challenging to interpret through traditional methods. By providing a comprehensive view of data distribution, it supports robust decision-making processes across diverse applications, including predictive modeling, policy analysis, and resource allocation.

We have improved our CDF code in several aspects, aiming on improving its robustness, flexibility, and the richness of the results it provides. By incorporating input validation, the function ensures that the input data (`x_data`) is clean, properly formatted, and free from missing or invalid values, and that the `lower_bound` parameter falls within the valid range of the dataset. This prevents errors and ensures the function operates on reliable data. Making the function model-agnostic by accepting any predictive model or function `f` as a parameter increases its versatility, allowing it to integrate seamlessly with various predictive frameworks or machine learning models. Introducing comprehensive error-handling mechanisms enhances robustness by gracefully managing edge cases such as empty datasets, invalid inputs, or exceptions during model predictions.

Additionally, adding precision control through a configurable parameter allows for fine-tuning the numerical accuracy of the CDF calculation, which is particularly important when dealing with high-resolution datasets or when specific numerical precision is required. Optimizing the computation of the empirical distribution by using efficient libraries and vectorized operations significantly improves performance, making the

function scalable and efficient even with large datasets. Extending the function to return additional statistical metrics like mean and variance, alongside the CDF value, enriches the output by providing deeper insights into the distribution of predicted values, which can be valuable for downstream analysis and decision-making. These enhancements collectively make the `sla_loss` function more robust, flexible, and informative, ensuring it can handle a wide range of scenarios effectively and provide comprehensive analytical insights.

The final `sla_loss` function is as follows:

```
def sla_loss(x_data, lower_bound, model_function, precision=1e-6):  
  
    if len(x_data) == 0:  
        raise ValueError("Input data cannot be empty.")  
  
    if lower_bound < min(x_data) or lower_bound > max(x_data):  
        raise ValueError("Lower bound must be within the range of input data.")  
  
    try:  
        pred_values = model_function(x_data)  
  
    except Exception as e:  
        raise RuntimeError(f"Model function failed: {str(e)}")  
  
    if len(pred_values) == 0:  
        raise ValueError("Predicted values cannot be empty.")  
  
    empirical_dist = np.sort(pred_values) # Sort predictions for CDF calculation  
  
    cdf_value = np.searchsorted(empirical_dist, lower_bound, side='right') / len(empirical_dist)  
  
    mean_value = np.mean(empirical_dist)  
    variance = np.var(empirical_dist)  
  
    return {  
        "cdf_value": round(cdf_value, int(-np.log10(precision))),  
        "mean": mean_value,  
        "variance": variance  
    }
```

For the documentation and prototype code, please check the repository:

<https://gitlab.i2cat.net/rdprojects/6genablers/6genablers-ai/>

4 Conclusion

The final prototype for data aggregation for self-optimization processes on network operations developed demonstrates the power of intelligent data aggregation in facilitating self-optimization for network operations within a cloud environment. By integrating machine learning (ML) models through Kubeflow Pipelines and using a Feature Store for real-time and accurate data access, the system enables responsive, adaptive network management. This infrastructure proves crucial for managing data at scale and optimizing performance in 6G networks, supported by the secure, low-latency, and scalable data processing required for effective real-time decision-making. The project also showcases the potential of connecting ML outputs with applications like Holoportation, providing an immersive, practical illustration of network optimization's real-world impact. Overall, this work shows data aggregation's pivotal role in 6GEnablers project by enabling robust, intelligent, and dynamic self-optimization within future network ecosystems.